

However, none of these complexes showed anomalous broad absorption between $1300-700\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and as such the acid salt structure with very strong $\text{O}\dots\text{H}\dots\text{O}$ is most improbable³.

From our previous¹ and present work with 2N1N, it is observed that donor property of 2N1N is greater than 1N2N towards alkali metal salts. A larger number of alkali metal salts form solid complexes with 2N1N than with 1N2N.

It has been further observed that 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, which has the same coordinating groups in the same position as salicylic acid and a higher pK value, formed adducts which were found to be stabler than the adducts of alkali metal salicylates, reported earlier.

Similarly acetyl salicylic acid formed relatively smaller number of complexes and with the benzoyl salicylates, only a few compounds were obtained. This may be due to the enhanced solubility of these adducts in absolute ethanol or due to the weak coordinating ability of the ligand. The alkali metal salts of the esters (methyl salicylate and phenyl salicylate) which are more basic did not give any such compound and the second ligands replaced the esters from their alkali metal salts.

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Copper(II) Complexes with Subnormal Magnetic Moments Derived from New Tridentate Schiff Bases

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TRIDENTATE dibasic Schiff bases are often unique in forcing the metal ions (II and III) to dimerise or polymerise and as a result metal complexes with unusual magnetic and structural properties are formed^{1,2}. This preliminary communication reports the synthesis, magnetic and spectral characteristics of copper(II) complexes with the Schiff bases derived from diacetylmonoxime and salicylhydrazide (Ia) or amino-guanidine (Ib) or cyanoacetylhydrazide (Ic).

Experimental

The Schiff bases were prepared by the reaction of diacetylmonoxime (0.05 mole) and the corresponding

hydrazinoderivative (0.05 mole) in aqueous ethanol. (Addition of equivalent quantity of anhydrous sodium acetate was necessary while using aminoguanidine hydrochloride). The ligands were recrystallised from aqueous alcohol.

Anal : (Ia) : m.p. $259^\circ - 260^\circ(\text{d})$

(Found : C, 55.70 ; H, 5.20 ; N, 17.60. Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$:
C, 56.16 ; H, 5.53 ; N, 17.86%)

(Ib) : m.p. $236 - 237^\circ(\text{d})$

(Found : C, 30.74 ; H, 6.44 ; N, 35.80. Calc. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_5\cdot\text{HCl}$:
C, 31.01 ; H, 6.20 ; N, 36.17%)

(Ic) : m.p. $186^\circ(\text{d})$

(Found : C, 45.80 ; H, 5.10 ; N, 31.20. Calc. for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$:
C, 46.15 ; H, 5.45 ; N, 30.77%)

General method of synthesis of the complexes :

An aqueous alcoholic solution of the appropriate Schiff base (0.01M) was mixed with a solution of copper(II) chloride dihydrate (0.01M) in the same solvent ; on adding dil.ammonia solution, dropwise to this resulting solution to have a pH around 6-7 the respective complexes precipitated out as coloured (green or brown) microcrystalline varieties. The complex, in each case, was suction filtered, washed with ethanol and dried at room temperature over fused calcium chloride.

Results and Discussion

The results of the elemental analysis (Table I) show that the complexes have 1:1 stoichiometry with the general composition $\text{Cu}(\text{SB})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ where SBH_2 represents a molecule of any of the three (Ia, Ib or Ic) Schiff bases. The extreme insolubility of these Cu(II) complexes in water and common organic solvents did not permit any determination of molecular weight of these species and at the same time indicated their polymeric nature. The magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes measured by the Gouy method using A.R. $\text{CuSO}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as calibrant, show the magnetic moments to lie in the range 0.83-1.34 B.M. (Table I) at room temperature. This value is lower than the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. required for an $S = \frac{1}{2}$ system. The subnormal magnetic moments observed for these Cu(II) complexes might be attributed to the significant spin exchange between the interacting Cu^{2+} ions.³

These Cu(II) complexes exhibit a characteristic band in the range 550-575 nm which is assigned to a spin-allowed d-d transition ; the other significant band at ~ 390 nm is the subject of much controversy and in a number of complexes it has been recognised as the characteristic band representing the Cu-Cu linkage.^{4,5} However, the high intensity of the 390 nm band in the

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA FOR Cu(II) COMPLEXES

Ligand No.	Empirical formula of the complex Cu(SB)H ₂ O	% Cu	% N	ω_{eff} (300°K) B.M.	Electronic spectra ^b λ_{max} (nm)
Ia	(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂)Cu.H ₂ O	20.01 (20.19) ^a	13.28 (13.36)	0.83	390, 570, 625(sh)
Ib	(C ₈ H ₉ ON ₂)Cu.H ₂ O	23.20 (23.28)	25.55 (25.64)	1.34	390, 550, 630(sh)
Ic	(C ₇ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂)Cu.H ₂ O	24.40 (24.31)	21.60 (21.42)	1.02	390, 570

^a. Values in parentheses are the calculated values.

^b. Electronic Spectra in Nujol.

present Cu(II) complexes may be due to ligand → metal charge transfer^{6,7}. The three infra-red bands of all the Schiff bases observed between 925 and 1020 cm⁻¹ (assigned to NO frequencies of the oxime group) are shifted to higher frequencies (viz. between 970 and 1190 cm⁻¹) in the Cu(II) chelates indicating that the oxime nitrogen is a potential bonding site in all the complexes^{8,9}. The i.r. band due to C=N grouping (including the oxamino group) located at 1600 and 1650 cm⁻¹ in the Schiff bases Ia and Ib respectively are shifted to lower frequency region (by 10-20 cm⁻¹) in the corresponding Cu(II) complexes showing the involvement of the azomethine nitrogen in bonding^{9,10}. The broad band at 1670 cm⁻¹ in Ic assigned to the C=N stretching frequency coupled with the amide grouping, disappeared in the Cu(II) complex with the appearance of new weak-band at 1610 cm⁻¹ suggesting that bonding has taken place through the amide group via enolisation and through the azomethine nitrogen at the same time⁹⁻¹². In Ia, the strong broad band in the 3 μ region assigned to ν (OH) of both oxime group and salicyl residue, is shifted to much lower frequency region (by about 300 cm⁻¹) in its Cu(II) complex suggesting involvement of both phenolic-OH (of salicyl residue) and oxime group (after deprotonation) in complexation⁹⁻¹². The broad strong bands at 3400 and 3360 cm⁻¹ observed respectively in Ib and Ic may be assigned to OH stretching frequency of the NOH group; this band either disappeared or became very weak in their Cu(II) complexes suggesting deprotonation and involvement of the oxime group in complex formation as advocated above. It appears, therefore, that all the three Schiff base molecules containing oxime grouping exhibit diacidic tridentate function in complex formation with Cu(II) giving polynuclear species.

The cryomagnetic studies on these Cu(II) chelates are in progress and details will be communicated in due course.

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Titrimetric Determination of Amines via Formation of 2,4-Dinitrobenzenesulphenamides

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ALIPHATIC amines can be determined with ease by acidimetric titrations, however, satisfactory acidimetric titrations of aromatic amines were impossible for a long time because the basicity of water and that of lower alcohols is too high. Visual or potentiometric determination of these bases in organic solvents with perchloric acid represented a great advance¹; however, those amines which contain negative substituents cannot be titrated². The bromination method does not enjoy wide popularity because there are so many interferences owing to the oxidizing and substitution properties of